

Improved method for the determination of pyrimethamine in body fluids by enhancement of fluorescence

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The method is based on the reaction of pyrimethamine with salicylaldehyde to form a fluorogenic salicylaldimine whose fluorescence is further enhanced by reacting with boric acid in glacial acetic acid-acetic anhydride. The fluorescence of the resulting boron complex is measured after destruction of unreacted salicylaldehyde with sodium metabisulfite. Detection limits of 4.0, 3.4 and 2.4 ng ml⁻¹ have been obtained for pyrimethamine in dichloromethane, plasma and saliva, respectively.

The use of pyrimethamine [2,4-diamino-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-6-ethylpyrimidine] (1) as a suppressant in antimalarial therapy is well-known. It is quite often administered in combination with a sulfonamide or sulfone. It is also used in rabbit and poultry feeds as a coccidiostat^{1,2}, often with sulfaquino-line and sometimes in the treatment of meningeal leukemia^{3,4}. There appears to be a renewed interest in the antimalarial activity of pyrimethamine probably because of the emergence of chloroquine-resistant strains of *Plasmodium*, and the combination of pyrimethamine with sulfonamides/sulfones in the treatment of endemic malaria⁵. Since pyrimethamine is used in combination with a number of other drugs, a sensitive and selective method is needed for its pharmacokinetics and determination in body fluids in the presence of other drugs.

Several methods have been reported for the determination of pyrimethamine in biological samples. These include colorimetry⁶, NMR spectroscopy⁷, gas chromatography^{1,8}, thin layer chromatography combined with spectrophotodensitometry⁴ and spectrofluoridensitometry⁹ and high-performance liquid chromatography with UV-detection^{2,10} and fluorescence detection¹¹. A solution spectrofluorimetric method has also been reported¹².

The simplicity, sensitivity and selectivity associated with spectrofluorimetry make this method valuable for the assay of pyrimethamine, especially when used in combination with other drugs in the treatment of malaria. In this communication, an improved sensitive method for the determination of pyrimethamine in plasma and saliva is described. The method is based on the reaction of pyrimethamine with salicylaldehyde followed by boric acid in acetic acid-acetic anhydride medium. The enhanced fluorescence of the resulting boron complex offers the advantage of lower detection limits than previously reported¹². As a direct (non-chromato-

graphic) method, it is remarkable to notice that no interference is observed from mefloquine nor from quinine ($\lambda_{\text{EXC}} = 250, 350$; $\lambda_{\text{EM}} = 450$ nm), the measured fluorophore being excited at 380 nm and measured at 480 nm. Neither mefloquine nor quinine fluorescence at 480 nm when activated at 380 nm.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of salicylaldehyde with amines has been used for the fluorimetric determination of compounds containing the amino functional group^{13,14}. This reaction is slow and requires activation by warming¹³. The reaction between pyrimethamine (1) and salicylaldehyde (2) results in an increased conjugation of the fluorophore with a corresponding increase in fluorescence intensity of the salicylaldimine derivative (3) compared to the weak native fluorescence of pyrimethamine or salicylaldehyde. The fluorescence of the salicylaldimine derivative was further enhanced by treating with boric acid in glacial acetic acid-acetic anhydride medium. The formation of boron complexes has been found to greatly enhance the fluorescence of salicylic acids,¹⁵

salicylamides¹⁶ and salicylaldehydes and *o*-hydroxyphenylketones¹⁷

The mechanism of enhancement of fluorescence of the salicylaldehyde derivative of pyrimethamine by boric acid in acetic acid-acetic anhydride medium is not adequately known. However, the fluorophore is most likely to be a salicylaldehyde-boron-acetic acid (1 : 1 : 2) complex (4). Trace amounts of moisture lead to cloudiness of the solution and drastically reduce the fluorescence of the boron complex. The addition of 0.5 ml of 0.1 M H₂SO₄-AcOH solution was found to obviate this. Heating the mixture for about 10 min at 50° was found to stabilize the boron complex and hence increase in the fluorescence.

Spectrofluorimetric measurement of the boron complex of the salicylaldehyde derivative of pyrimethamine (4) provided a suitable method for the determination of the drug after its extraction from plasma or saliva.

Linear calibration graphs were obtained by treating standard solutions of the drug in these body fluids as described. The results are shown in Table 1. Recoveries of 92.8 (±3.2%) and 95.6 (±2.7)% were made from plasma and saliva, respectively, by spiking 40 ng ml⁻¹ of pyrimethamine five times. One-half and twice this concentration were also spiked without significant differences in recovery results. The increased sensitivity inherent to fluorescence spectrophotometry makes this method suitable for the assay and pharmacokinetics of pyrimethamine in plasma and saliva.

Table 1. Calibration data for pyrimethamine in dichloromethane, plasma and saliva*

Pyrimethamine taken ng ml ⁻¹	Fluorescence intensity		
	Dichloromethane	Plasma	Saliva
0	17.9 (2.0)	39.3 (3.2)	23.8 (4.9)
10	21.2 (7.5)	41.5 (5.3)	29.8 (8.1)
50	22.2 (8.6)	46.8 (6.2)	33.3 (14.7)
100	27.8 (10.8)	53.4 (6.0)	40.7 (18.2)
150	32.3 (10.8)	62.1 (5.6)	53.3 (9.4)
200	40.8 (17.4)	67.0 (6.9)	58.9 (5.4)

*Each value is the mean of 6 determinations for dichloromethane and plasma and 4 determinations for saliva. The relative standard deviations (%) are given in parentheses. Regression equations are: for dichloromethane, $y = 0.104x (+0.111) + 0.28 (\pm 0.63)$, where y is the fluorescence intensity and x (ng ml⁻¹) the concentration of pyrimethamine (0–200 ng ml⁻¹), correlation coefficient $r = 0.9071$; for plasma, $y = 0.136x (\pm 0.060) + 2.04 (\pm 0.42)$, $r = 0.9116$; and for saliva, $y = 0.169x (\pm 0.094) + 1.94 (\pm 0.83)$, $r = 0.9567$.

The limits of detection for pyrimethamine in dichloromethane, plasma and saliva were found to be 4.0, 3.4 and 2.4 ng ml⁻¹, respectively.

Experimental

Dichloromethane and sodium metabisulfite (AnalaR) and glacial acetic acid (May & Baker) were used. Salicylaldehyde, acetic anhydride, boric acid, quinine sulfate, magnesium sulfate and glacial acetic acid were of reagent grade. Dichloromethane was distilled before use. Salicylaldehyde was distilled under reduced pressure. Quinine sulfate was recrystallized from hot water. Pyrimethamine was obtained by pulverizing 10 tablets of Daraprim (Wellcome) in distilled water (3 ml) and made alkaline with 1 M NaOH (2 ml). The slurry was extracted with dichloromethane (2 × 50 ml) and the extract was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate before evaporation. Elemental analysis and melting point (241–242°; lit.¹⁸ 239–242°) of the extracted pyrimethamine indicate a high degree of purity.

A 1% solution of boric acid in acetic acid (H₃BO₃-AcOH) was prepared and from this a 0.1% solution was obtained. Solutions of 0.1 M H₂SO₄ in acetic acid, 10% aqueous sodium metabisulfite and 0.2% salicylaldehyde in dichloromethane were prepared. Fluorescence was measured on a Perkin-Elmer 204 spectrofluorimeter.

Reaction between salicylaldehyde, pyrimethamine and boric acid: A 5 ml aliquot of a 5% solution of salicylaldehyde in dichloromethane was added dropwise to a solution of pyrimethamine (0.2487 g, 0.001 mol) in dichloromethane (30 ml). Then acetic anhydride (2 drops) was added, and after 15 min at room temperature with occasional shaking, the reaction mixture was reduced to a smaller volume (~5 ml) by evaporation. The mixture was warmed on a water-bath at 60° for 10 min after adding 10% aqueous solution (1 ml) of sodium metabisulfite. After removing the aqueous layer, residual moisture was removed by the adding anhydrous magnesium sulfate and filtered. Any pyrimethamine absorbed by magnesium sulfate was extracted by washing the magnesium sulfate thrice with small quantities of dichloromethane. The filtrate was evaporated almost to dryness, the residue treated with acetic anhydride (1 ml), 1% H₃BO₃-AcOH solution (0.5 ml) and 0.5 M H₂SO₄-AcOH solution (0.5 ml) and kept at 50° in a water-bath for 10 min. On evaporation to dryness, pale cream-white boron complex was obtained which gave only one spot when examined by TLC (silica gel; dichloromethane : methanol, 70 : 30, v/v). Detection was made by exposure to iodine vapor. The boron complex was examined for fluorescence and the excitation and emission wavelengths that gave maximum fluorescence intensity were established as 380 and 480 nm, respectively.

Detection limits for pyrimethamine in dichloromethane, plasma and saliva: A 1.0 ml aliquot of drug-free dichlo-

romethane was evaporated to dryness and the residue treated with glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml) and 0.2% salicylaldehyde (0.5 ml). It was evaporated to dryness, 10% sodium metabisulfite (1.0 ml) added and the mixture was heated on a water-bath at 60° for 10 min to destroy unreacted salicylaldehyde.

This was extracted with dichloromethane (2.0 ml), the organic extract evaporated to dryness and then mixed with acetic anhydride (1.0 ml) followed by 0.1% H₃BO₃-AcOH (0.5 ml) and 0.1 M H₂SO₄-AcOH solution (0.5 ml). The resulting mixture was kept at 50° for 10 min before measuring the fluorescence at excitation and emission wavelengths of 380 and 480 nm, respectively. The procedure was repeated ten times.

For the determination of detection limits in plasma or saliva, drug-free plasma (or saliva) (1.0 ml) was made alkaline (pH 12) by the adding 2 M NaOH (0.5 ml). After adding dichloromethane (5.0 ml), the mixture was shaken for 1 min and centrifuged for 10 min. The organic layer was evaporated to dryness and the residue treated with acetic acid, salicylaldehyde, acetic anhydride, boric acid and sulfuric acid solutions in turn as for the dichloromethane blank. The fluorescence intensity was then measured as described above for the dichloromethane blank.

Detection limits were calculated as the concentration of pyrimethamine that gave intensities two standard deviations of the blank above the mean blank signal.

Calibration for pyrimethamine in dichloromethane, plasma and saliva. A 0.1 ml aliquot of a stock solution containing 100 ng ml⁻¹ pyrimethamine was diluted to give a working solution of 100 ng ml⁻¹ pyrimethamine in dichloromethane. Aliquots (0.1–2.0 ml) of the working solution (corresponding to 10–200 ng of pyrimethamine) were placed in test tubes and the dichloromethane was carefully evaporated (water-bath 60°). The residues were treated with 0.1% acetic acid (0.5 ml) and 0.2% salicylaldehyde solution (0.5 ml). The mixtures were shaken for 2 min and kept at room temperature for 15 min before evaporation to dryness. Ethanol (0.5 ml) was then added, agitated briefly and warmed on a water-bath (60°) for 10 min after adding 10% sodium metabisulfite (1 ml). Subsequent operations and measurement of fluorescence were carried out as described above.

For the preparation of calibration graphs for pyrimethamine in plasma (or saliva), aliquots (0.1–2.0 ml) of the above working solution (10–200 ng of pyrimethamine) were evaporated to dryness as described above. To each residue was added drug-free plasma (or saliva) (1.0 ml) and the mixture was shaken for 30 s. The resulting solutions were made alkaline (pH 12) with 2.0 M NaOH (0.5 ml). After the adding chloroform (5.0 ml) to extract pyrimethamine, the mixtures were shaken for 1 min and centrifuged. The organic layer was removed and treated as described above for the determination of detection limits in these fluids. Six determinations were made for plasma and four for saliva, each accompanied by a blank determination.

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